

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 01st February 2022

Accepted: 05th February 2022

Online: 10th February 2022

KEY WORDS

religious texts, theolinguistics, interpretation of Qur'an, hadiths, religious scientific books, religious dictionaries, religious publicistic works, va'zs (sermons), texts of praying.

In Uzbekistan, as in all spheres, “the situation with religious freedom has dramatically improved. Further strengthening inter-ethnic harmony and inter-religious tolerance is a constant task for us” (1). Researches in the field of linguistics also play an important role in fulfilling this task. In our country today, a number of scientific studies are being conducted to study the relationship between linguistics and religion.

The study of sacred texts on religion dates back several centuries. The study of the linguistic features of the Qur'an began in the seventh century, and it was by the study of Qur'an that the science of

ABOUT THE CLASSIFICATION OF RELIGIOUS TEXTS

Yusupova Shahzoda Tohirjon kizi

Sayidrahimova Dilfuza Sayidmahamadjanovna

PhD on Philology, Tashkent State University of Law, Uzbekistan

Professor of Russian Academy of Sciences, PhD on philology, Kyrgyz-Uzbek University, Kyrgyzstan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6045882>

ABSTRACT

Classification of written and oral religious texts based on Islam is given in this article.

linguistics developed and the schools of linguistics in Basra and Kufa were founded. Also, the issues between religion and language were initially studied in detail by philosophers, theologians, sociologists, psychologists. Later, on the basis of a new paradigm in linguistics – anthropocentrism, theolinguistics emerged to study the features of religious linguistics.

Religious texts are a type of texts related to religious traditions, reflecting the central concepts of religion, religious beliefs and religious instructions. Oral and written religious texts based on Islam in the Uzbek language can be divided into some groups:

The interpretation of Qur'an

Hadiths

Religious scientific books: scientific texts on tajvid, hadith, history of Islam, fikh and other directions

Terminographic and encyclopedic religious dictionaries

Religious publicistic works

Religious va'zs (sermons)

Texts of praying

1. Sacred religious texts. The group includes interpretation of Qur'an in Uzbek. The peculiarity of sacred texts is that, it was not written by humans, it was downloaded by the Creator. In the years of Independence, translations and interpretations of Qur'an have been published. The Interpretations by Sheikh Alouddin Mansur, Sheikh Abdulaziz Mansur and Sheikh Muhammad Sodik Muhammad Yusuf are famous among the public.

2. Hadiths. Hadith is a type of text that consists of advice and suggestions of Prophet Muhammad (may peace be upon him), it contains historical features in itself. (A.Rahimov, A.Abduqodirov and H.Qodirova, B.Valiyevs worked on linguistic features of hadith in the Uzbek linguistics).

3. Religious scientific texts. This group contains books and works written by religious scholars on learning Qur'an, the science of hadith, fiqh, tajvid and other

disciplines. This kind of texts are mostly written for scientists. But today the development of religious science, people's wishes on learning the religion, the need to learn the religious matters broader caused to learn this type of books by folk. This presents the feature of religious texts – being scientific and popular at the same time. A variety of books, created in the years of Independence, especially, the books of Sheikh Muhammad Sodik Muhammad Yusuf are the examples for this type of books.

4. Terminographic and encyclopedic religious dictionaries. "Encyclopedia of Islam", Arabic-Uzbek encyclopedic dictionary "Al-Qomus" by N.Ibrohimov, Arabic-Uzbek dictionary "An-Na'im ul-kabir" by O.Nosirov, M.Yusupov, Yu.Rahmatullayev, A.Nishonov, dictionary called "Religious terms and expressions" are included in this group.

5. The group of religious publicistic texts. The group covers mass media

materials (monthly pressed journals like "Hidoyat", "Mo'minalar" and a weekly pressed newspaper "Islom nuri" and others), TV programs ("Hidoyat sari" and others) and internet sites on religious purposes.

6. Religious va'zs (sermons). Religious va'zs (sermons) are read by religious scholars and imom-khatibs.

7. The texts of praise. Praise is important in religious belief, people try to communicate with the Creator by the help of praise. Therefore, praise is specific for everybody. The texts of praise have oral

and written types, they are found in oral speech, belles-lettres style, scientific books on religion and in religious publicistic works.

Leaning on the ideas above, we can say that religious texts have their own types, that can be identified as genres, and this can be a factor to differentiate religious functional style. Like other types of text, religious texts can also be the object of study for textlinguistics; religious texts differ from other texts by the characteristics of such text types.

REFERENCES:

1. The speech of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the 75th session of the Head Assembly of the UNO. 23.09.2020//<https://president.uz/uz/lists/view/3851>
2. Encyclopedia of Islam. –Tashkent, 2017. –672 p.
3. Gulbakhor, R. (2020). Expression of temporality and locality through noun lexemes in Mahmud Kashgari's "devon". *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(11), 1648-1653.
4. Ibrohimov N. Al-Qomus. (2017) Arabic-Uzbek encyclopedic dictionary. –Tashkent.
5. kizi Yusupova, S. T. (2019). STUDY OF RELIGIOUS FUNCTIONAL STYLE IN THE WORLD LINGUISTICS. *Scientific Bulletin of Namangan State University*, 1(12), 173-178.
6. Mahbuba Rasulova Ravshan qizi. (2021). EXAMINING APPLICABLE METHODS AND TECHNIQUES TO FOSTER EFL LEARNERS' SPEAKING SKILLS. *Eurasian Journal of Academic Research*, 1(9), 549–563.
7. Nosirov O., Yusupov M., Rahmatullayev Y., Nishonov A. (2014) An-na'im ul-kabir. Arabic-Uzbek dictionary. –Namangan. –810 p.
8. Qizi, Y. S. T. (2020). Religious speech and phonetic interference. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(6), 679-683.
9. Rahimov A. Hadis janri haqida //Til va adabiyot ta'limi. 1995, –№ 5-6. –P.38-42.
10. Rozikova, G. Z. (2019). SEMANTIC FEATURES OF LEXEMES BELONG TO THE GROUP OF NAMES OF PERSON APPLIED IN "DEVONU LUGOTIT TURK". *Scientific Bulletin of Namangan State University*, 1(12), 136-141.
11. Yusupova, S. T. (2019). CHARACTERISTICS OF RELIGIOUS FUNCTIONAL STYLE OF THE UZBEK LANGUAGE. In *АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ВОПРОСЫ СОВРЕМЕННОЙ НАУКИ* (pp. 20-21).